

Bankim and Rabindranath:

Dialectics in the Dawn of the Age of Bhadrakok

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Abstract: This article speaks of certain landmark conflicts and clashes of ideas involving Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay and Rabindranath Tagore, which shaped the trajectory of our history, marked the end of the Bengali Babu (also spelt as baboo) and marked the birth of the age of Bengali Bhadrakok. This article revisits the respective legacies of Bankim and Rabindranath for Bengal's long twentieth century. This article will observe in Bankim and Rabindranath – in each of them – some defining moments of conflicts, which are rich sites of dialectics, and which, as this article will argue, facilitate a strange mutation of history and transform the obviously comprador motif of babu into an ambivalent figure of bhadrakok. These conflicts come to shape the history of the age of Bengali bhadrakok. We shall see how the cultural, political and historical dimensions of the bhadrakok, and the forces of historical contradictions in the twentieth century Bengal were shaped by the respective strategies, positions and ideologies of these clashes, centrally involving two of the greatest cultural icons of modern Bengal, Bankim and Rabindranath, who very often were polar opposites in these significant clashes of ideas.

Keywords: Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay, Rabindranath Tagore, Bhadrakok, Nationalism, Bishshomanob, Universal Human(ism), Bengali People, Bengali History and Culture in the Long

Twentieth Century.

A Note on Transliteration: In this article I have tried to adhere to transliterations which faithfully reproduce the sounds of Bengali words, unless a familiar transliteration rules out the possibility of such adherence, e.g. Rabindranath and not Robindronath, owing to reasons of familiarity. While a person (or entity, event, organ etc) not already very well-known in a certain spelling in English will have his or its name transliterated in the Bengali way (and not in the received Sanskrit way), the same person's surname might have been spelt traditionally, again owing to reason of familiarity, e.g. Chondi Choron Sen. On the vexed issue of a Bengali standard of transliteration (or the lack thereof), one can see my article "Spelling of Ognijug: A Case for a Bengali System of Transliteration" in the site of Journal of Bengali Studies, which I wrote as a response to the controversy arising out of our spelling, Ognijug (and not the Sanskrit Agniyuga or the hybrid Agnijug/Agniyug). Finally, let me express my regret at any inconsistency in transliteration which might persist in this article. My individual attempt is no compensation for the general lack of any Bengali standard of transliteration to this date.

A Note on the Scope of the Study: I have not been able to chronicle all the debates, arguments and conflicts which involved Bankim and Rabindranath, because that would require much larger space, and the study would assume encyclopedic proportions. So, I have tried to limit myself to some of those clashes which I consider to be **representative** conflicts. Further, compared to Bankim, Tagore is usually much more minutely documented in a plethora of studies undertaken by our scholars, and while Tagore's opponents have been generally unfavorably dealt with by our critics, commentators and cultural historians, the histories of such conflicts are nevertheless well preserved, something that we cannot always say about the life and times of Bankim. Let me reassert that this study is not a comprehensive documentation of all the clashes of ideas which concerned Bankim and Rabindranath. For example, one significant exclusion, owing to time-space constraint, which I regret, is that I have not dealt with Rabindranath's debate with Bipin Chandra Pal, who stood by

nationalism as a political ideology and criticized Tagore for what he perceived to be the escapism of a political self—development. As Bipin Pal during this conflict belonged firmly to the camp of C R Das, and I have dealt with other important members of that camp who clashed with Tagore, that probably compensates this exclusion, no doubt in a very insufficient manner though. Then, I have not been able to deal with Rabindranath's clash with Jadunath Sarkar, who criticized Tagore's workings in Visvabharati and Tagore responded with extreme aggressiveness to Jadunath's criticism, which remains one of the few instances when Rabindranath launched a vitriolic attack against his opponent publicly (Ghosh 1: 121-2). Tagore's inner-contradictions and his conflicts with the luminaries of his age are well documented by Nityopriyo Ghosh in his three-volume study, and that should be used for further reading by anyone who is interested in this matter. One major exclusion in case of Bankim (due to time-space constraint, again) is that I have not discussed Bankim's debate with Reverend W. Hastie, Principal of General Assemblies Institution. Hastie was a Christian missionary who attacked the idolatry of Hinduism following the newspaper report of a massive *shraddho* ceremony at Shovabajar Rajbari in 1882 which was attended by all sections of educated Bengali gentlemen, a fact that scandalized Hastie who then launched a vituperative against the importunate idolatry of western educated Bengalis. Hastie's article spoke of Hinduism as a "monstrous system" and its gods and goddesses as "personations of evil" and Hindu spirituality as "psychological conditions of disease"; Bankim, then serving as deputy magistrate in Cuttack produced his rejoinder under the pen name of Ram Chandra. Hastie responded back, and the debate was lengthy. Though Bankim wrote letters under a pen name, his authorship of these letters was not a secret, and later Rev K M Banerjee who entered that debate directly spoke of Ram Chandra as author of *Kapalkundala*. The debate was carried out in the *letters* section of *The Statesman*. Bankim's last letter in this debate did not use a pen name and was signed by himself (*Essays and Letters* xiv-xxii).

In discussing these conflicts, I shall not strictly stick to chronology, and will move to and fro,

because analogies inherent these battles and connecting patterns underlying these ideological clashes are far more interesting than any tedious categorization by dates. This article deals with **contemporary** clashes of ideas which involved Bankim and Rabindranath, and does not deal with any challenges posed to these icons by future writers.

One major reason why I feel the necessity of producing this article (apart from the willingness to revisit and re-interrogate the respective legacies of Bankim and Rabindranath) is that the very idea of clashes and conflicts becomes an anathema to bhadrakalok sensibility which generally wants to transcend all divisions which separate one set of humanity from another, and though that age is arguably over, we still are saddled with its characteristic prejudice which prohibits us about talking conflicts even when we are surrounded by them.

I own the sole responsibility of translations of Bengali sources into English.

The figure of the babu should not be simply dismissed as a mere collaborator of the British, as the babu was also a preparatory process of history that paved the way for Bengal Renaissance. David Kopf quotes from Bhabanicharan Bandyopadhyay to exhibit that the babu had some noteworthy qualities apart from being a mere pawn of the empire. While his western education aimed at dissociating him from his ancestral customs and his community, he was richly exposed to the intricacies of world history, politics, philosophy and literature. The babu had “modern, cultivated habits evidenced by his support of educational and cultural reforms. ... Because of his patronage of printed works, bookstores had multiplied in Calcutta” (213).

Against the Triumvirate: Bankim clashes with Brahmo, Ancien Regime and Comprador

The babu was by no means the lone inhabitant of the colonial world, and he existed within an ecology of diverse interests. The westernized Brahmo existed by the side of Hindu ancien regime, for example. Such forces existed together in nineteenth century Bengal; they contributed to the perpetration of the empire and to the deferral of the rise of nationalist resistance. I shall proceed to discuss a set of minor and unrelated clashes that Bankim was involved in, with three minor and unrelated figures: three very minor figures who were fortunate enough to become the subject of Bankim's criticism, and they together constitute an interesting triumvirate, in my opinion. I propose to discuss these clashes briefly because these clashes and these figures have a *representative* quality. Together these three figures could almost constitute a three-headed hydra, albeit on a very miniscule level. Such a hydra ultimately nurtured the interests of empire and deferred the rise of Bengali nation-consciousness. Bankim's life-long project was national awakening of the Bengali people, so these clashes have an air of inevitability.

Minor and trivial in themselves, these three figures represent three important power centres of contemporary Kolkata.

1. Chondi Choron Sen, a Vaidya by caste and a justice in the colonial judicial system. We take him as a representative comprador.
2. Ramgoti Nyayrotno, a Brahmin by caste and a voice of Sanskritist conservatism. We take him as a representative of Hindu ancien regime during colonial times.
3. Koilash Chondro Singha, a Kayastha by caste, an employee of Jorasanko Tagores and a spokesperson of the Brahmos.

I shall start with Koilash. Bankim is known to be economical in his critiques. His critical economy straightaway called Koilash a servant of the Tagores of Jorasanko. Koilash indeed was a *Nayeb* or zamindar's deputy for the Jorasanko Tagores. Koilash was also the assistant secretary of *Aadi Brahmo Shomaj*. In that **truth** debate with Rabindranath, to the details of which we shall turn our

attention shortly – that direct battle which took place between Rabindranath and Bankim – Koilash was the first one to fire a salvo at Bankim (Tagore then followed suit, but more of that later).

Bankim is brief and devastating towards Koilash in his article “Aadi Brahmo Shomaj O Nobo Hindu Shomproday” (2: 764). Koilash’s name was known to Bankim, as he sporadically used to write against the Bankim in Brahmo periodicals. But the one which drew Bankim’s wrath was an article by Koilash in the Brahmo mouthpiece *Tottwobodhini* which alleged that Bankim was thieving (*toshkorbritti*) from the works of the likes of Bhau Daji, Mitra, Hunter and other researchers. Koilash decried Bankim’s supposed lack of originality and denounced his allegedly “blind” dependence on translations without any ability to go through the originals. Koilash also warned Bankim to refrain from mentorship (*Gurugiri korio na*). Bankim does not care to respond to these insulting charges coming from a nondescript Brahmo employee, but just scathingly calls Koilash a servant (*bhrityo*) and calls his language *nayebi* (nayeb-like). *Nayeb*s were a stock motif in popular literature culture as sycophants of their bosses and offensive to the common people.

The Brahmo panic at Bankim’s project of Hindu/Bengali nationalism was understandable and the eventual Brahmo decline is forewritten in this minor clash. Bankim would emerge victorious, and Hinduism will rapidly dethrone Brahmoism in the age of bhadralok.

Now, we come to Ramgoti Nyayrotno. He is taken to be an exemplary representative of the Sanskritist school of Bengali writing by Bankim in his article “Bangala Bhasha” (2: 322-3). Ramgoti was a crusader against the intrusion of colloquial in written script, and wants to banish the language of *Aalaler Ghorer Dulal* (the masterpiece by Peary Chand Mitra) from Bengali literature. Bankim examines Ramgoti’s own prose style used in that Sanskritist proposition, and observes that Ramgoti himself writes in colloquial language to reach the readers. Bankim further exposes the paradox of Ramgoti’s position that advocates prudery and wants to banish the colloquial on the pretext that the same is not suitable for discourse between the elder and the younger members of the family. Bankim lampoons this position by giving some imaginary examples of mother-child and

father-son conversations in chaste Sanskrit. That the linguistic ancien regime represented by the likes of Ramgoti wants to banish jolliness and mirth from the language of literature was obvious to Bankim, whose brief critique also mentions that Ramgoti's sole forte is Sanskrit, and though he is without any knowledge of western literature, he nevertheless tries to show some scholarliness in English which has the effect of creating unintended humour. Ramgoti wants "Bidyashagori Bangla" (Bengali of Vidyasagar, heavily laden with Sanskrit) and Bankim's act of taking a firm position against that language had a lasting effect on the medium of literature of the age of bhadralok (we shall come back to that ideological conflict between Bankim and Vidyasagr). Further, it had the effect of freeing Bengali from the clutches of Sanskritists, as in his article, Bankim mostly supports the position taken by Shyamacharan Gangopadhyay, whom Bankim takes as the representative of the Bengal school (demanding greater closeness of Bengali literature to Bengali people's language of everyday use).

Now, the last man of the triumvirate, Chondi Choron Sen. Sen was a munsef of Krishnanagar, as Bankim tells us, and in a judgment Sen wrote that 99% of Hindu widows are unchaste (*oshoti*). Bankim was brief in his rejoinder (2: 769), and in his response he offers an anecdote. A guru came to the house of his disciple, who then got ready a curry of ten big koi fishes as a welcome lunch. Guru ended up eating all the nine fishes and the disciple was rather frustrated at this economy of leaving just one fish as proshad (the remnants of food served to the guru, known as proshad, is traditionally meant for consumption by the disciple). Bankim compares the economy of Chondi Choron's judgment with the anecdotal guru's gluttony and mocks the logic behind sparing the last one out of a hundred; Bankim advises Chondi to write a fresh judgment that would include the remaining one percent. Here Bankim's brief castigation of an Anglophile, Bengaliphobic member of colonial baboodom is memorable as a part of his strategy of attacking the comprador classes. It is this strategy of Bankim which was instrumental in the transformation of the baboo to bhadralok. The bhadralok will not hate his roots, but the babu often did.

While Bankim acted as the cultural and intellectual fountainhead for Ognijug and the revolutionary fervour of the age of bhadrakok, Rabindranath Tagore could be seen behind the universalist turn of bhadrakok and the subsequent dream of a world community, and such worldviews during twentieth century were the forte of left and liberal ideology.

Tagore was also the fountainhead of a significant trend in the age of bhadrakok: a denial of the local and a desire to move to the universal. Whenever, for example, conflicts between Hindus and Muslims or between Bengalis and non-Bengalis took place in the twentieth century, there has been a marked bhadrakok tendency to disregard such petty clashes. By aligning himself with the universal brotherhood of man, the bhadrakok manages to escape his responsibility to stand by his community, his people. As a result, whenever Bengalis were at the receiving end, rarely a Bengali intellectual spoke up for his people, because he is primarily fueled by an anxious aspiration to claim the status of bishshomanob. Let us take an example.

Liberal Rabindranath versus the Partisans of Religion

Kolkata experienced a violent riot on 2 April 1926. At the end of the day, official estimate of death was 45, wounded 584. It all started when a Hindu religious procession was passing by a mosque in Jorasanko. In response to that event, Tagore wrote his famous poem “Dhormo Moho” (Illusion of Religion): *Dhormer beshe jaare moho eshe dhore/ Ondho she jon maare aar shudhu more...Je pujar bedi rokthe giyeche bheshe/Bhango bhango aaji bhango tare nihsheshe/Dhormokarar prachire bojro haano/E obhaga deshe jnaner aalok aano.* (roughly translated as: One who is grabbed by illusion in the guise of religion/That blind man only kills and gets killed.../The altar of worship that is flooded with blood/Break, break, break that today till it’s finished/Strike the walls of the prison of religion with thunder/Bring light of knowledge to this unfortunate land). Tagore also delivered a speech during this period where he made some interesting propositions: that religion is personal, and it should never be used as a public instrument, and it should never be used as the basis of

forming a community, and that religion needs to be countered with atheism. Sabyasachi Bhattacharya gives a detailed account of Tagore's response to the 1926 riots and tells us that this speech was never compiled in Tagore's collected works, probably because of that open advocacy of atheism to eradicate religion (*Shobhyotar Shorup* 73), which might have been an embarrassment for Brahmo establishments. However, the poem quoted above indeed gives a similar kind of impression. The poet offers Enlightenment as a solution to the problem created by religious conflicts.

The nature of what Tagore proposed here was quite striking: he wanted to live in that futuristic utopia when Enlightenment has replaced religious clash, and he did not want to take any stand in the present, when he might have some obligation to speak out against the initial violence started by a particular party.

Here we may contrast that approach of Tagore with Satin Sen's Satyagraha movement in Potuakhali, Barisal, which experienced a communal clash of an exactly similar nature: Hindu procession passing by a mosque leading to unrest. Waiting for the dawn of enlightenment which will eventually banish religion from public life is a liberal's futuristic utopia that absolves him to take a side *in the present*, here and now. As opposed to that Tagorean approach, Satin Sen began a painstaking movement of Satyagraha demanding the right of the Hindus to carry out religious processions. Further, when Saraswati Pujo was being banished in some of the schools of Potuakhali, Satin Sen fought for the right to conduct worship of the Goddess of learning in the schools. Strikingly, Tagorean approach brings us to a very awkward moment when City College came to a standstill regarding Saraswati Pujo in 1928. Tagore, maintaining his Brahmoist, anti-idolatrous as well as pro-Enlightenment stand, was against Saraswati Pujo in the Rammohan Roy students' hostel

of City College, and Satin Sen, along with Subhash Bose during this period stood by the students.¹

Nityopriyo Ghosh also gives an account of this incident. When a fees boycott movement by students left City College financially vulnerable, Tagore sent one lakh rupees from the resources of

Visvabharati. He also denounced the ‘biased’ stand of politicians like Subhash Bose in this matter (1: 127). While Tagore himself was not always free from bias on most issues, he had a penchant to imagine himself to be above all petty strife while he perceived those who disagreed with him to be partisan. His own anti-Saraswati bias remains questionable, and perhaps his Shantiniketan, remaining true to his legacy, till date does not allow Saraswati pujo inside its campus.

Tagore’s approach had a long-term implication for the age of bhadralok. While his idea of an idol-free, religion-free utopia could never sufficiently dislocate the religious and cultural anchorings of the Bengali community which continued to celebrate Saraswati Pujo and other festivals, it indeed helped to subdue them to an extent where any partisan stand in response to an attack on the idols, culture or members of one’s community, an attack on religion and identity is deemed slightly embarrassing, if not outright offensive. The ethnic attacks on Bengali speaking Hindus in Assam or Bangladesh never elicited any substantial response from the bhadralok. Odia onslaught on Bengal’s history was likewise overlooked. What the bhadralok was supposed to do under such circumstances was to theorize the events to some universal import and suitably undermine any partisan membership of one’s own community. Such tendency might lead to the dissolution of a community, as common sense would say. Such a bhadralok tendency with Tagore at its source is not the result of any isolated stance of Tagore, but a consistent position which he often (though not always) maintained from his early career.

The Pratapaditya Debate: Rabindranath vs Sarala Debi

A striking feature of the impending clash of ideas which will shape the outlook of the impending age of bhadralok is that the two iconic thinkers of this age were writing two of their representative works simultaneously as the dawn of this age was looming large on the horizon. Bankim’s *Anandamath* was being serially published in *Bongodorshon* between 1287 and 1289 (Bengali Years), and during the same period Tagore’s *Bou Thakuranir Haat* was being published in *Bharoti*,

and then both the novels were issued in book format in January 1883, as Nepal Majumdar tells us (1: 62).

Nepal Majumdar throughout his multi-volume study of Tagore maintains an avowed Tagorean stance, and his criticism of Bankim is audibly loud: “Bankim already authored *Durgeshnandini* (1865), *Mrinalini* (1869), *Chandrashekhara* (1875), *Rajsingha* (1882) etc which are fundamentally nationalist and valorizing texts of historical romance. In literature that was an age of extreme nationalism” (1: 62). In the same vein, Majumdar declares: “In that age of pungent nationalism, instead of painting Pratapaditya as an ideal warrior hero Rabindranath painted him as cruel and malicious. ... Rabindranath was not possessed by the ghost of historical romance of warrior heroes. Rabindranath wanted to create a novel. He never fabricated history by colours of imagination and falsity to search for national valour, bravery, love for freedom and military superiority” (1: 63).

Tagore observes in his preface to his collected works: “The emotional flood of Swadeshi movement wanted to paint Pratapaditya as the ideal hero of Bengal, and that flood still has not receded. Whatever information I gathered from history about him gave me proofs that he was an unjust, tyrannical and cruel person, and though he had the inexperienced arrogance to disobey the God of Delhi (*Dillishwar*), he lacked power” (qtd. in Nepal Majumdar 1: 63). It is interesting to observe that Tagore diligently stuck to this agenda of demolishing Pratapaditya; after thirty years of publication of *Bou Thakuranir Haat*, wrote a play titled *Prayoshchitto* based on the same story.

However, Nepal Majumdar’s claim about Tagore’s strict observance of historicity (a claim Tagore himself made too, as we can see) lacks substance. Tagore’s statement that Pratapaditya was merely driven by inexperienced arrogance is severely ahistorical. Pratapaditya spent many years in the court of Akbar where he was kept as a collateral guarantee so that revenues would be sent to Fatepur Sikri by the kingdom of Jessore. It was in the Mughal court that Pratapaditya learnt the intrigues of the empire and learnt about many successful rebellions against Mughal authorities from different parts of India which inculcated in him a desire for freedom, as Satish Mitra’s book attests

at length. Pratapaditya was a crafty and able politician and was anything but inexperienced in the skills of warfare and administration.

Tagore comes from a clan of Bengali Brahmins called *Pirali*, some of the ancestors of whom were collaborators of the Muslim rulers in the medieval period and were converted to Islam. While in Bengali we have no synonym for the word comprador, *Pirali* could be a close equivalent. Tagore might have inherited a softness to foreign rulers, and his celebrated idea of *bishshomanob* might have stemmed from that *Pirali* inheritance, as we shall see later: imperialism loves *bishshomanob*. Tagore authors a celebrated poem about Shah Jahan where he paints the Mughal emperor as an ideal lover-poet, but in personal life Shah Jahan was not any less cruel or tyrannical compared to Pratapaditya. While the humble ruins of the empire of Jessore is no match for the grandeur of a Mughal Tajmahal, and Dillishwar has a mighty ring to it that Joshoreswor utterly lacks, Tagore's hostile treatment of an indigenous Bengali fighter against Mughal supremacy leaves much to be desired.

However, so far as Rabindranath's claim of strict observance of historical accuracy in portraying Pratapaditya is concerned, it is saddled with problems, as we have already seen. While Tagore continues his Pratap-bashing in *Prayoshchitto*, his play of 1315 (Bengali Year), in that he adds a new element: a non-violent rebellion of the subjects against Pratapaditya led by a saintly character named Dhananjay Bairagi. This was Tagore's fabrication of history. It goes without saying that no such rebellion against Pratapaditya is historically known. Tagore's portrayal of Mughal collaborator Basanta Ray as a benign figure is sentimental and ahistorical, and Satish Chandra Mitra in his magnum opus *Jessore Khulnar Itihash* contends that Rabindranath's depiction of Jessore kingdom and Pratapaditya had serious historical anomalies (2: 722).

When Sarala Debi starts Pratapaditya festival in 1903, Tagore is reputed to have said: "Sarala is enthusing and stamping her feet about a murderer" (সরলা একজন খুঁননী ললাককক লইয়া মলাতলামলাতত ও

দলাপলাদলাতপ কতরকতকছ). In her response, Sarala says that she is worshipping the valour of Pratapaditya. (Nepal Majumdar 1: 323). A detailed description of the Pratapaditya *utshob* (held on 1 Boishakh, the day of Pratapaditya's coronation) is recorded by Sarala in her autobiography *Jiboner Jhorapata* (121-2). Sarala is candid in her admission that it was a strategy arising out of necessity and quotes Bipin Pal who quipped: "As necessity is the mother of invention, Sarala Devi is the mother of Pratapaditya to meet the necessity of a hero for Bengal" (122). Sarala further writes that Tagore was "extremely angry" at Sarala for starting Pratapaditya festival that undid Tagore's depiction of Pratapaditya in *Bou Thakuranir Haat*, and to convey his anger, Tagore sent Dinesh Sen as an emissary to her. Sarala stood by her position. She was clear on this: Pratap was not a moral ideal, but a political ideal. In his declaration of independence, in his valour, Pratap was "politically great". Dinesh Sen never came back with Rabindranath's response to that position of Sarala (123).

However, that would not be the only instance when Tagore was displeased at Sarala. In certain respects, Sarala was one of the earliest legacy-bearers of Bankim Chandra in Bengali public life, and a clash with Rabindranath was bound to take place. Sarala laments in her autobiography that "there is no establishment to preserve an ever vigilant memory of Bankim in the minds of the Bengalis," while Tagore is propagated by VisvaBharati (41). She also responds to the **truth** debate between Bankim and Rabindranath in the beginning of *Jiboner Jhorapata* with clear sympathies for Bankim, granting only the benefit of a children-friendly ideal of morality to Tagore's position (that Tagore's moral position in favour of absolute truth was only suitable for children, and that it could not be a matter of ethics for grown-up people).

When Sarala registered her affinity for Hinduism, in spite of being a Brahmo herself, and attended the ritual of evening *Arati* at the Vishweshwar temple of Varanasi, Rabindranath Tagore was mortally wounded; he was agitated and angry, and asked Sarala: "This is how you indulge in idolatry? Indulge in falsehood?" (*Jiboner Jhorapata* 73).

At the time when Bankim was no more, and someone had to provide intellectual leadership to the

rising nationalist aspiration, Sarala boldly took on the mettle. It was a difficult task for her, because it meant that she had to face the personal wrath of the greatest living intellectual of her age, her own uncle, Rabindranath Tagore, but nonetheless, she did not step back. History might attest that Sarala's courage and her ability to challenge Rabindranath did not go in vain. The slogan Vande Mataram became the chant of revolution, thanks to Sarala's leadership. While Sarala was close to Vivekananda. She was also the first choice for Vivekananda to propagate the message of a resurgent Hinduism in India and abroad (when her parents did not agree, then Vivekananda went for sister Nivedita), as Sarala records with some details in her autobiography. Sarala's personal acquaintance with two of the greatest icons of Hindu revival, Bankim and Vivekananda, and the icon of Bengali liberalism, Rabindranath Tagore, places her in a very unique position.

Mousumi Biswas Dasgupta wrote in her review of Sarala's autobiography that Sarala was both the Maud Gonne and Joan of Arc of early Ognijug (154). While the subtextual irony of such an evaluation of Sarala cannot be missed (Maud was socialite and Joan was warrior; and these different qualities from different periods could not be conjoined without some irony of history), and that Sarala herself acknowledged the political nature of her project of inventing a hero, her role in this clash of ideas shaped the ethos of Ognijug and helped nurture a military spirit among Bengalis. Vande Mataram was a war cry, and the Pratapaditya debate shaped the moments of the birth of that war cry to some extent.

***Nyakami* and D L Roy's Farce: Tagoreans in Action**

In Bengali there is a word, *nyaka* which is an adjective; it signifies the quality of pretending. The word seems to have come from *neki*, which is virtue in Islamic parlance. It probably originated as a derision on someone who pretended to be virtuous. This word, *nyaka* and the noun formed by adding the suffix -mi to it, *nyakami*, together constitute a set of pejorative criticism of anything that

is not just pretension, but might also lack the manly qualities of straightforwardness, and might indulge into a sort of effeminate behavior. D L Roy considered Tagore and his brand of poetry to be *nyaka*.

This is one familiar objection against a type of modern poets and poetry that was repeated in the short story *Kochi Shongshod* by noted humorous writer Parashuram (Rajshekhar Basu), so D L Roy was not alone in considering a certain brand of contemporary poetry *nyaka*. While gender stereotypes offer a sense of comfort to patriarchy in general, and therefore a conservative panic at Tagore's supposed poetic *nyakami* might not have any sympathy from us today, we need to remember that Bengalis were long berated as non-martial and effeminate by the British, and that the nascent nationalist struggle wanted to challenge that stereotype. While we think of stereotype, let us remember that there are many stereotypes; the effeminate stereotype of the Bengali babu was an imperial construct, and Bengal's newfound valour in the Swadeshi era might have looked at the trend of Tagore's poetry with some amount of apprehension and disapproval. Because what patriotic writers like D L Roy perceived to be *nyakami* would precisely confirm the imperial stereotype of Bengalis as an unworthy and unmanly people lacking virility and only good enough to write meaningless gibberish passed as poetry.

As per the preface to the collected works of Dwijendra Lal Roy, *Anondo Biday* (Goodbye to Anondo) was the last farce that Dwijendra Lal Roy wrote and it is assigned to the date of 16 November 1912 (2: 28). However, Nityopriyo Ghosh tells us that it was originally written and published in the *Bongobashi* magazine in 1904 as a response to Tagore's *Kori O Komol*. It was eventually re-published in a revised format in November 1912, and was staged on 16 December 1912 (1: 50). This was considered to be a personal attack against Tagore, but D L Roy himself maintained that it was not a personal attack and was an attack against certain trends:

There is no personal attack in this small play. ... Feigning, precociousness and stupidity

(*nyakami*, *gyathami* and *bokami*) have been sufficiently ridiculed. If anyone has an inner inflammation (because of my play), he is responsible for that himself, not me. ... If a poet considers a type of poetry malevolent, it is his duty to whip such poetry and throw it out of the field of literature. Browning whipped the great poet Wordsworth once. (qtd. in preface to *Dwijendra Rochonaboli* 2: 28)

D L Roy castigates what he perceives to be a corrupting, lascivious and feigning trend in Bengali poetry indulging in mindless obfuscations. *Anondo Biday* still was felt to be a personal attack on Tagore, as Dwijendra Lal Roy publicly criticized Rabindranath on similar charges already. There were mainly two accusations: obscurity and lasciviousness; D L Roy said that vagueness is not depth, because even the water of a pit is usually opaque, and that Rabindranath's poetry had only the libido (*lalosha*) but not devotion (*bhokti*) of Vaisnava poetry (Ghosh 1: 51).

D L Roy castigated Rabindranath on these charges for the first time in his article "Kabyer Obhibyakti", and that in 1906, a caricature of Rabindranath's supposed effeminate style of recitation was performed at a meeting of D L Roy's *Purnima* Club (Ghosh 1: 46).

The followers of Tagore exacted revenge on the day of performance of *Anondo Biday*: "Tagore-admirers collectively went to Star theatre and sat strategically scattered in the auditorium, in the second scene Satyendranath Dutta threw his shoes at the stage, then the Tagoreans chased D L Roy himself and force-stopped the performance" (Ghosh 1: 51).

In his response, D L Roy claimed that the correctional criticism of his play of 1904 already showed its results and that Tagore's contemporary poetry was comparatively free from the excess of libido; further, he asked in agony: "Is Rabindranath God, and is any criticism of his books religiously proscribed?" (Ghosh 1: 50).

A familiar conservative position against effeminacy, the ideological stance of Roy against Tagore

is creatively expressed through a lampoon of lyrical love poetry in *Anondo Biday*. As a noted maker of heroic and patriotic drama, D L Roy probably considered it to be his poetic duty to purge elements which he considered undesirable in Bengali literature in that age of national awakening. However, the very preface to D L Roy's collected works bear the brunt of the lasting grudge of Tagoreans who dominate the Bengali scholastic industry; apart from very casual errors of factual details, the preface goes on to declare that *Anondo Biday* is unsuccessful as art, that there is no dramatic unity and inevitability in the play (though the preface writer does not make it clear what is meant by inevitability, *onibarjota*), that there is nothing noteworthy in the play barring a few comic songs and that it does not carry any new artistic promise in D L Roy's career; the preface mentions in a casual tone that the spectators of the play could not *tolerate* (italics mine) the personal attack (2: 29).

In the beginning of the play *Anondo Biday*, Anondo laments about his son Nepal who speaks in a nasal tone, keeps long hair, and maintains a melancholic gaze at the sky. He keeps poetic company, all of whom have the same features. Nepal plays flute and has a theatre group where he is planning to stage a play titled "Up-to-date Krishnaleela."

The charge of effeminacy was a haunting experience that the Bengali babu had to face. Bankim himself turned a crusader against effeminacy in "A Popular Literature for Bengal": "And it would be difficult to conceive a poem more typical than the *Gitagovinda* of the Bengali character as it had become after the iron heel of the Musalman tyrant had set its mark on the shoulders of the nation. From the beginning to the end it does not contain a single expression of manly feeling – of womanly feeling there is a great deal – or a single elevated sentiment" (*Essays and Letters* 17). His evaluation is questionable, but understandable in the context of his age. However, Bankim was not blind to the significance of the feminine principle, *prokriti*, as a scholar of Samkhya.

Coming back to *Anondo Biday*: it is called a parody: there is a musical play named *Nondo Biday* by Atul Krishna Mitra (1888) and this play by Roy is a parody of that play. Interestingly, nobody

considered it to be an attack on Atul Mitra, and though there is only one explicit mention of Rabindranath's name, along with other poets like Michael, Hem and Nabin (D L Roy 2: 537), which is by no means offensive, still there is absolute consensus among the contemporary and present day critics that the play is an attack on Tagore. If Tagore's poetry is not *nyaka*, which it is not indeed, barring some exceptions, then this play should not be considered to be a **personal** attack on Tagore. However, Tagore's admirers themselves might have responded to this play with a conviction that the play was a lampoon on them, and in this regard, D L Roy cleverly ended up proving his point: the poetry which he attacked to be full of pretension readily owned up the charge and since then got into a mode of counter-attack. The preface to D L Roy's collected works is marked by the same counter attack that continues till date: Roy is castigated in the preface of his own collected works by the preface writer.

Roy in his farce critiqued the vain and concocted expressions full of mindless abstraction in what he considered to be *nyaka* poetry. The counter-attack against Roy keeps on emphasizing that it was in fact a personal assassination of Tagore. This challenge that was posed to what D L Roy perceived to be decadence in poetry, was moral in nature, and perhaps not personal.

The sentimental individualism of Tagore's poetry eventually won, and the likes of D L Roy lost. The age of *bhadralok* had a lyrical, individual, non-narrative and non-heroic sensibility in poetry. Tagore's absolute dominance in poetry was the force behind that sensibility. Heroic and historical sensibility, which propelled D L Roy to attack the poetry of pretension, soon would become a thing of the past, but not before it would motivate Haraprasad Shastri to pass his dismissive remark on Tagore's *Gitanjali* to which we now turn our attention.

Chutki: Haraprasad Shastri Assails Tagore's Nobel Winning Gitanjali

There was some consternation when Tagore was awarded Nobel prize for the text *Gitanjali* and

Haraprasad Shastry remarked that it's a book of trivial sketches. The Bengali word that Haraprasad used in his presidential address in the *Bongiyo Sahityo Shommeloni* of 1321 (Bengali year) was *chutki* which variously means the snapping of fingers, comic sketches, and small pieces of anecdotes. This constituted a grave offence for the Tagore supporters, and Satyendranath Dutta, Tagore's loyal follower wrote a poem lampooning Haraprasad. The entire episode is noted in Sukumar Sen's introduction to the first volume of Haraprasad Shastry's collected works (19). While this episode of history itself is just a brief sketch, *chutki*, because no lengthy battle directly took place between Haraprasad and Rabindranath, but Haraprasad's historical imagination, which makes him the worthy disciple of Bankim's quest for a history of the Bengali people, was probably behind that remark. Ahistorical, individualistic lyricism of Tagore earned international accolade, but did not earn appreciation from the likes of Haraprasad who were searching for the roots of Bengali identity.

The Nationalism Debate

One of the first registered protests against Tagore's speeches on Nationalism, first in America and then in Japan (in 1916) came from Chittaranjan Das, and we shall presently come to that. It should be mentioned that Tagore's lecture on nationalism in Japan offended the Japanese people, and he was henceforth cold-shouldered by the Government and boycotted by the Japanese Press which denounced him as a "poet of a defeated nation" as Nepal Majumdar chronicles (1: 409). Not to be subdued by such adversity, Tagore went on to deliver his nationalism speeches in America where he declared that "nationalism is a great menace", and air was rife with rumours that the members of the Hindustan Gadar Party based in America would assassinate the poet for betraying the Indian struggle for independence, as Nepal Majumdar records. (1: 413)

Nepal Majumdar, in spite of being the avowed Tagorean that he is, correctly observes that Tagore's critique of nationalism is as widely off the mark as possible. For example, it is capitalism and not nationalism which should have been at the centre of Tagore's vitriolic attack when he says:

“the living bonds of society are breaking up, and giving place to merely mechanical organization ... man is driven to professionalism for producing wealth” (1: 418). Further, in the same vein, Tagore’s statements criticize imperialism, but he tries to pass it off as a critique of nationalism. Throughout his nationalism treatise, we find that Tagore tries to proceed in an unscientific and sentimental manner. Nepal Majumdar comments:

Tagore was not habituated in thinking along the lines of modern social science and politico-economical perspectives... while he is out there to attack capitalism and imperialism, he ends up claiming that nationalism is at the root of all evil. ... Rabindranath did not properly realize the progressive role played by nationalism in the anti-imperialistic struggle in the colonized countries including some of the European countries” (1: 420-1).

In his enthusiasm to criticize nationalism, Tagore even announced that it was also responsible for the growing separation between man and woman: “It is owing to this that war has been declared between man and woman, because the natural thread is snapping which holds them together in harmony; because man is driven to professionalism producing wealth for himself ... leaving woman alone to wither and to die or to fight her own battle unaided” (qtd. in Nepal Majumdar 1: 418). In this slightly eccentric way, Tagore could have blamed nationalism for cancer, diabetes and asthma as well; the sinking of Titanic and the growing number of road accidents and the air pollution in the industrialized cities – they all could be attributed to nationalism, if we extend Tagore’s whimsical logic.

In the present researcher’s opinion, Tagore’s identification of nationalism with capitalism and imperialism is question-begging to say the least, and is not fit to be considered as social science or philosophy. However, Tagore’s *Nationalism* still remains a guiding light of liberal spirit among Bengalis and Indians. One of the most oft-quoted works of Tagore, *Nationalism* has been repeatedly used as the ultimate and final word on this subject. That the age of bhadralok could be successfully

weaned from revolutionary nationalism and brought to communist internationalism could be argued to be a result of Tagore's relentless onslaught on nationalism. It might not be a mere coincidence that in Lenin's library, Tagore's *Nationalism* in German and Russian translation was available, with some passages personally underlined by Lenin (Nepal Majumdar 1: 422).

Chittaranjan Das in his speech titled "Bangalar Kotha" registered his protest against Tagore:

In Europe, some scholars supposedly have decided that the Nation-idea is completely imaginary and its foundation lacks any substance. A specific nation has no independent value. ... To nurture a sense of nationality is to increase the clash between nations which will harm mankind. This is an old theory, but currently it is being propagated anew, so a few pundits in our country have grabbed that theory and are trying to laugh away our nascent nationalist aspirations. This theory coming from Europe was disproved by great scholars of Europe in the past, and I hope they will do the same this time. They will solve their own problems. But the sand is hotter than the sun. These fake pundits in our country have so much of scholarship that their propositions can never be disproved. So much so, that the Rabindranath who prayed to God for the soil and water of Bengal to be made true during the Swadeshi movement, that Rabindranath is now Sir Rabindranath – this time in America has stood by that theory with a lot of gusto. His complete speech has not been published in any paper. So, we could not read that, but in *Modern Review* some of the excerpts were quoted, and we have read that, and may be we are under a wrong impression for not having access to the whole, but whatever has been published, that proposition, in this case, in my opinion, from this position of this great assembly of the Bengali nation should be opposed.

This proposition is fully based on the immaterial shadow of the *bishshomanob* (universal human). In order to raise a true sense of fraternity in humankind, all different nations must be developed. Prior to that, this idea of fraternity is fanciful imagination. If you abolish

nations, where does the *bishshomanob* stand? (20-21)

C R Das in his presidential speech to the Gaya Congress again spoke about the same idea of nationalism as an indispensable step towards universal humanity:

Now what is Nationalism? It is, as I conceive, a process through which a nation expresses itself and finds itself, not in isolation from other nations, not in opposition to other nations, but as part of a great scheme ... I contend that each nationality constitutes a particular stream of the great unity, but no nation can fulfil itself unless and until it becomes itself and at the same time realize its identity with humanity” (qtd. in Nepal Majumdar 2: 161)

While C R Das repeatedly evokes the necessity of the flourish of all nations as a pre-requisite for universal humanity, he does not state the obvious (apart from dropping a mild hint, when he says *Sir Rabindranath*); that such idea of universal human will only help the empire and will further debilitate the colonized Bengali people.

A Marxist perspective on the debate between universalism and nationalism is offered by Terry Eagleton, which similarly manages to reconcile nationalism with the eventual objective of universal humanism, taking cue from the Marxist idea of class struggle eventually paving the way for a classless society. But in addition, it adds a cautionary note that any premature abandonment of nationalism will make one's nation vulnerable to oppression by other nations.

“Nationalism,” remarks an African character in Raymond Williams's novel *Second Generation* (London 1964), “is in this sense like class. To have it, and to feel it, is the only

way to end it. If you fail to claim it, or give it up too soon, you will merely be cheated, by other classes and other nations.” Nationalism, like class, would thus seem to involve an impossible irony. It is sometimes forgotten that social class, for Karl Marx at least, is itself a form of alienation, canceling the particularity of an individual life into collective anonymity. Where Marx differs from the commonplace liberal view of such matters is in his belief that to undo this alienation you had to go, not around class, but somehow all the way through it and out the other side. To wish class or nation away, to seek to live sheer irreducible difference *now* in the manner of some contemporary post-structuralist theory, is to play straight into the hands of the oppressor. (23)

In Ireland too, the empire promoted universalism. In his study on Irish cultural history, *Crazy John and the Bishop and Other Essays on Irish Culture*, Eagleton mocks the colonized subject who attempts to sublimate his concrete humiliation within the empire into the abstraction of universal humanism: “If you are a second class subject in Britain, you can always compensate by becoming a citizen of the world, which is a grand way of being a citizen of nowhere” (104). In fact, it has been observed that all empires since antiquity have promoted universal humanism. Tagore’s *bishshomanob* is thoroughly fit to be an imperial construct. Steven Grosby observes: “Furthermore, throughout history, empires, such as the Roman and Ottoman, have sought to unify their people as a political alternative to nations. Thus, while an individual often understands himself or herself as a member of a particular nation, one may also recognize oneself as a part of humanity” (4).

One major charge that Tagore repeatedly brings against nationalism is that it is a foreign import, that it does not belong to India, that the word or the concept has no equivalence in our languages, and that our history, religion, ethics, society, home – they do **not** accept the dominance of nation-making (Nepal Majumdar 1: 196). C R Das responds:

Some are saying that it is improper for us to take any pride in nationalism. Because this idea of nation is completely an import from the West. ... the eternal relation of a certain country with its countrymen, only on that foundation the nation can be established, the relation which is eternal and will be forever, it's just that so far, our attention was not drawn to that. May be in our civilization and in our flourish no specific name was given to this relation. It may also be that if Europe's civilization and flourish, their education and initiation, their science and history did not come upon our heads so rapidly, we would not have been conscious so early and easily – but does that mean what is our own, what belongs to our country, what is attached in every particle of Bengal's soil and water, we shall call that a western import and insult the entire Bengali nation? (24)

Tagore's universalist position disregards the local, and in many respects. While he dismisses the nation in favour of the *bishshomanob*, he also dismisses the local possibilities of exceptions to his universalizing theory. The imposition of the universal and the dismissal of the local, the celebration of the eternal and disregard of the historical, the denunciation of the relative and an upholding of the absolute, the denial of the concrete and a faith in the ideal – these are repeated motifs in Tagore (though it would constitute a familiarly Tagorean injustice if we universalize Tagore in this manner; let us acknowledge that he sometimes took the other side too). Such a trend was visible in the early career of Tagore. We shall now turn our attention to a very important clash of ideas, what I call the **truth** debate.

The Truth Debate: A Direct Battle That Bankim and Rabindranath Fought with Each Other

Bankim in his article “Aadi Brahmo Shomaj O ‘Nobo Hindu Shomproday’ ” (published in *Prochar* Ogrohayon 1291) responded to an invective of Rabindranath Tagore directed at Bankim that was

first given as speech in an Aadi Brahma Shomaj meeting, and published in the Brahma mouthpiece, *Bharoti*. The issue of contention was centred on Bankim's statement that truth is relative and not absolute, and that virtue lies not in external propriety but the intention behind an action. Bankim was founding an ethical ideal in Krishna, and came up with some interesting instances where the person strictly speaking the truth or strictly adhering to codes of religious rituals can actually be harmful while a person who utters a lie for saving a life or saving a situation, or who casually violates the ritualistic codes, is actually virtuous. Bankim might or might not have the Brahma cult and fan-following for absolute truth in his mind. As an emergent Hinduism needed to uphold its Puranic ideals, so mercilessly dismissed by a semi-Abrahamic Brahma cult of monotheism/monism, Bankim probably had that Brahma cult of truth in his mind when he was offering an alternative idea.

He might have the same motive when he was establishing the dualism of Samkhya at the root of Hinduism, while the Brahmans celebrated the non-dualism of Vedas. It might have been a veiled challenge to the Brahma cult of truth, when Bankim charted his discourse about the relativity of truth, but we cannot be certain about that.

Certainly the Brahma leadership was apprehensive about Bankim's agenda of Hindu revivalism in *Krishnacharitra*, and the attack on Bankim carried out by Tagore takes place within that context of anxiety. Bankim comes across as someone remarkably free from dogma in this entire debate. Bankim aims at ethical and moral codes which are both compassionate and pragmatic, not impersonal and idealistic. Bankim emerges victorious out of this battle of ideas. The Brahma side is not known to have been able to have responded properly to Bankim's arguments.

Here Bankim comes across as a leader of Hindu revival, and Rabindranath Tagore in this argument is the cogent face of Brahma reaction following a volley of personal attacks hurled at Bankim by Koilash Singha, an agent of Thakurbari (the Tagore house, the supreme family of Aadi Brahma Shomaj). Bankim's article repeatedly refers to the cordial relationship that he shares with

the young Tagore, and does not reveal any great sense of injury following Tagore's attacks. In the beginning of his article, Bankim says that he has been subject to such attacks even before Rabindranath Tagore learnt how to read and write, and that he is no longer agitated by such personal onslaughts.

While this battle of ideas in itself might not have any great significance beyond the immediate moment of challenge posed by an emergent Hinduism (as Bankim was evoking the ancient Indian idea of *Satya* that is closer to the archaic English word truth, and not the limited, restricted and narrow concept of truth) to the Brahmo hegemony, it is nevertheless imperative for us to note that that it creates a template for the age of bhadrakalok. Less abstract and more sensual, less impersonal and more compassionate, less idealistic and more pragmatic, less universal and more historical – this template probably was too close to perfection to be followed. Power relations within a society will always dictate ideological terms, and Bankim does expect too much from human agents who are not sovereign authors of their action. Bankim's article indeed suggests that Tagore was merely acting as a mouthpiece of Brahmos in this debate. Sarala Debi thinks otherwise though; she says Tagore's elder brothers Dwijendranath and Jyotirindranath were opposed to him in this issue and had sympathies with Bankim (41); nevertheless, a sizable section of Brahmos believed in the cult of absolute truth, it cannot be denied.

It can be argued that the Brahmo cult of truth had a certain Anglocentric Protestant ethos at its kernel (at least the similarities are striking). Bankim observes that there is just a lip service to truth while the heart is full of untruth in this western cult imported from England. While the verbal "lie direct" is objected to, but a sea-load of sins are allowed within this western paradigm. Brahmo cult of truth at the end of the day was a colonial idealism.

Tagore's vociferous opposition to nationalism, we have already seen, had the same impersonal, ahistorical, universalist, idealist dogma which he first exhibited in this debate with Bankim. In the nationalism debate too, just like in this truth debate, Tagore acts as a mouthpiece of liberal

intelligentsia which was panic-stricken at the rise of revolutionary and violent nationalism in Bengal. The age of bhadrakal eventually had to abandon the nationalist template offered by Bankim, and gradually came to be dominated by the idealist template offered by Tagore.

Tagore vs Sharatchandra: The Anti-Colonial Debate

This constitutes a matter of common knowledge in Bengali literary history that *Pother Dabi* became a bone of contention between Sharatchandra and Rabindranath after it was banned by the British government (Tagore refused to condemn the banning and considered the British regime to be quite liberal in allowing voices of dissidences to be heard; Shishir Kar chronicles in details). But before venturing into that, we should briefly discuss about the antecedents and aftermath of the publication of *Pother Dabi*, though not necessarily in that order.

Gopalchandra Roy in his celebrated biography of Sharatchandra notes that the text ended up having a soaring popularity after it was banned, and single copies were sold at princely sums of one hundred rupees (the printed price was three rupees), and even handwritten copies came into existence owing to the popular enthusiasm around *Pother Dabi*. Further we know from Gopalchandra Roy that every raid at the dens of revolutionaries of Bengal was sure to yield copies of two particular books during this period, as the police commissioner seems to have admitted: *Gita* and *Pother Dabi* (146).

Pother Dabi reportedly had an interesting history of genesis. The aforesaid biography, *Sharatchandra* threw some interesting light in this regard. Let us take an excerpt:

Shailesh Bishi in his *Biplobi Sharatchandrer Jibon Proshno* (The Life Enquiry of

Revolutionary Sharat Chandra) further recounts – “Sharatchandra said, ‘While you were not here, Mr Caulson, Police Commissioner of Kolkata, came to meet me. He invited me for tea at his residence. When I went, his wife made tea herself. Mr Caulson requested me to write a book like Tagore's *Char Odhyay*’ (a novel of Tagore that showed the revolutionary nationalists in a negative light).

I (Shoilesh Bishi) said, ‘if you write a novel like *Char Odhyay*, you better burn down *Pother Dabi*’.

Dada (Sharatchandra) said, ‘you will get to see’.

This was probably the time when he wrote *Bipradas* – but *Dada* couldn’t do a *Char Odhyay* and ended up erecting a zamindar figure to offer a hotchpotch.”

This account of Shoileshbabu creates an impression as if Sharatchandra agreed to write a novel like *Char Odhyay*. But that is obviously not the case. Because, in this regard another information is known from Surendranath Gangopadhyay’s account. Surenbabu has written – “one day some Mr Prentice called on Sharatchandra and asked – you write a book like *Pother Dabi* on the Government’s behalf (that is, an inverted image of *Pother Dabi* that denigrates the revolutionaries). You will get a handsome amount of money.

Sharatchandra replied – *Shaheb*, my childhood was spent with flying kites and spinning tops. My youth in cannabis and opium. Then I went to Rangoon for job. I no longer have the acumen to write *Char Odhyay*. You pardon me.

Far apart from writing a book like *Char Odhyay*, we get to know from the account of Charuchandra Roy, the revolutionary of Chandernagore, that Sharatchandra wrote *Pother Dabi* precisely as a protest because Rabindranath wrote *Ghore Baire*. Sharatchandra himself told that to Charubabu, as Charubabu records in his discussion of Sharatchandra’s *Shesh Proshno*. (423)

In this connection, we remember Tagore's foreword to *Char Odhyay* where he recollects a private interview with Brahmabandhab Upadhyay who allegedly expressed regret for his role in the swadeshi movement. It created controversy, because Brahmabandhab was dead by then, and there was no way to establish the veracity of such an encounter; raising a dead man as witness, and using a private conversation with him to score a point against the revolutionary movement in Bengal might not have been in good taste on Tagore's part, and that was probably the reason why he removed that foreword in the next edition (Kar 118).

Renowned Hungarian Marxist critic Georg Lukacs called Tagore's novel *Ghore Baire* (The Home and the World) a propaganda of British police in his celebrated review of *Home and the World* titled "Tagore's Gandhi Novel". When the imperial machine was leaving no stone unturned to blemish the revolutionary movement in Bengal, Tagore's novel did a considerable damage by playing straight into the hands of the British. In fact the timing of Tagore's novel itself had a damaging effect, as Nepal Majumdar notes: "When *Ghore Baire* was being serially published in *Shobujpotro*, at that time (9 September 1915) five Bengali boys under the leadership of Bagha Jatin faced the innumerable strength of British Police and Military with unmatched courage" (1: 403).

While Tagore was idealistic in demanding a flawless social revolution, and ended up aiding the empire, Bankim too might have been idealistic in demanding a pure literature and unwittingly ended up imposing the contemporary Victorian ideal in our literature. We shall now turn to that.

Bankim's Aversion of BotTola: Where Does the *Chhotolok* stand in the Age of Bhadraklok?

Bankim's Kamalakanta visited a bazaar in his opium induced dream, and saw the cultural products of his day in the shape of fruits; in that market, Bengali books were green plantains (*kanchkola*, and the word is also used idiomatically to imply nothingness or worthlessness).

This was largely the shape of things as perceived by the educated Bengalis. Bankim in his articles “A Popular Literature for Bengal” and “Bengali Literature” gives us a very clear impression of his dismissal of a large part of the existing Bengali literature as uncouth and not fit for educated society. This was the dominant attitude of his day: the learned Bengali babu were particularly hostile to what he perceived to be the immorality and obscenity of a large part of Bengali literature. As a result, what was otherwise to be judged by indigenous standards, and not by standards borrowed from the west, ended up being removed and obliterated from the fields of Bengali literature following strict Victorian moral codes. Bankim’s unsympathetic castigation of his own mentor Ishwar Gupta in the article “Bengali Literature” is a case in point, and Bankim’s sympathetic foreword to the selected works of Ishwar Gupta is another interesting case in point. In both of them Bankim emphasizes the identification of Gupta’s quality of writing with a bygone era that has gone away for good. In his foreword Bankim says: “*Ekhon aar khanti Bangali kobi jonme na – jonmibaar jo nai – jonmiya kaaj nai*” (“the pure Bengali poet is no longer born now – his birth is no longer possible – his birth is no longer of any use”) (*Rochonaboli* 2: 706).

Bankim might not have realized, but it was a surrender to the ideology of British empire, submission to a sensibility which was a foreign and imperialistic implant. This single statement probably encapsulates the Achilles heel of Bengal renaissance, as the dissociation with the roots was bound to manifest itself in a number of cultural maladies, one of them being a growing isolation of the elite from the masses, a rift which is perhaps one of the major factors which brought the final end to the age of bhadrakal in 2011, as future ages will probably argue.

In the article “Bengali Literature” Bankim makes the following observations on Ishwar Gupta:

He was a very remarkable man. He was ignorant and uneducated. He knew no language but his own, and was singularly narrow and unenlightened in his views; yet for more than twenty years he was the most popular author among the Bengalis. As a writer of light satiric

verse, he occupied the first place, and he owed his success both as a poet and as an editor to this special gift. But there his merits ended. Of the higher qualities of a poet he possessed none, and his work was extremely rude and uncultivated. His writings were generally disfigured by the grossest obscenity. (*Essays and Letters* 32)

However, Bankim qualifies his critical assault on Gupta with some riders: “Strange as it may appear, this obscure and often immoral writer was one of the precursors of the modern Brahmists. The charge of obscenity and immorality mainly applies to his poetry. His prose is generally free from both vices, and often advocates the cause of religion and morality.” (*Essays and Letters* 33)

Obviously, a filtering process is at work here. This is not just about filtering Ishwar Gupta, and the legacy that he left behind, but about filtering the good from the bad; the uncouth from the polished; the approved from the censored; the native from the cosmopolitan, the hybrid Bengali from the pure Bengali. The latter has to go, the former has to stay. This process robbed Bengali language and literature some of its popular, precious legacies. This process disinherited us and disempowered us to a great extent. Losing our past, and losing our roots and losing significant methods and genres and formats of cultural production left us anemic. While Europe celebrated the vulgar and the popular, the age of bhadrakalok lacked its Rabelais. It lacked colour and it lacked wildness. It lacked the ability to revive the spirit of the predecessors. It failed to discuss ancient and medieval Bengal without projecting its own westernized aspirations and dimensions. Chaste and politically correct, the age of bhadrakalok thus begins its long trek towards a dissolution of the **chhotolok** (literally small folk; it also means vulgar people, plebian people; it is the antonym of bhadrakalok). It was not necessarily a class offensive against the downtrodden, though. The elite cultures of indigenous origin were equally disrupted and mutilated. Any indigenous culture, be it mass or esoteric, elite or poor, which did not conform to colonial norms could be chhotolok culture. Sadly, as the age of bhadrakalok began, what was a gain in terms of sophistication, was a loss in terms of virility and

versatility of the Bengali soil. Bankim in this case was bound by zeitgeist of his age, which was heavily tilted in its judgment in favour of high culture as opposed to the low. Bankim continued in his aforesaid article in the same vein:

Ishwar Chandra Gupta is now fast falling into oblivion and we must proceed to notice the class of writers who have superseded him. But before doing so, we must premise a few words on the present general condition of Bengali literature.

One of the most noticeable characteristics of Bengal at the present day is the large amount of literary activity to be found there in comparison with other parts of India. But while books and newspapers are daily pouring in from our press, the quality of our current literature is by no means proportioned to its bulk. In fact, by far the greatest part [of] what is published is absolute rubbish. There are several modern Bengali books of which we shall have to speak in terms of high praise, but the number of these is so small in comparison with the mass of publications yearly vomited forth by the Bengali press... (*Essays and Letters* 34)

This attempt to separate the wheat from the chaff ended up as a process of getting severed from the indigenous roots, styles, forms and modes of writing. The age of bhadralok thus lost some valuable resources which could have enriched us. Bankim was a prisoner of his age in this regard. The age of bhadralok, thus born with a lopsidedness and an unresolved dialectics, since then has grappled with the problem of elitism.

Where does the **chhotolok** stand in the age of bhadralok? This is an important question, though searching for an answer of that question is beyond the scope of this article. But the tremendous tragedies of displacement and ethnic cleansing which befell the plebian members of the Bengali nation in the twentieth century have generally been overlooked by the bhadralok, whose elitism

might have facilitated his indifference. The dominant ethos of the age did not favour the rise of any sturdily indigenous pen with its arsenals of popular idiom and political incorrectness which could rectify the elitist bias of our Victorian codes and Enlightenment-derived worldview of the age of bhadralok.

Babu was a comprador. While the bhadralok challenged the empire in many respects, he still could not sufficiently rescue the pre-Christian (and pre-Islamic) voices of his ancestors in their pristine entirety (scholars like Haraprasad are notable exceptions, and even in Haraprasad, Victorian prudery is at work at times, when he denounces the vulgarity and decadence of our Tantric Buddhist past). A course correction of the trajectory of bhadralok in this regard was much required, but never adequately took place. True, the age witnessed some attempts to recover the folklores and folksongs, and became interested in baul etc, but these were often addled with projections of liberal western aspirations. Sincere attempts to revisit the pre-colonial indigenous roots of our culture are rare, though Ishwar Gupta's project of preserving *Kobigaan* was one such pioneering work which provided a template for the later ages to follow. Barring few brilliant exceptions, the age of bhadralok ultimately surrendered to imperial aesthetics.

To be fair on him, while Bankim could not salvage this situation, he did the best to preserve whatever remnants of the past that he could preserve. He was ready to let the past perish, as it was beyond his ability to find a way to keep the past alive, as the dominant sensibility of the Victorian-imperial complex was against that, but he was **not** ready to let it perish **unstudied**. Like Ishwar Gupta tried to retrieve *kobigaan*, Bankim tried his best to retrieve the works of Ishwar Gupta. Forces at work in our colonial history were hostile to the development of an indigenous Bengali aesthetic sensibility. The resultant loss to Bengali literature is heavy, no doubt. When we discard the low, we also discard a whole part of our body of legacy that lies beneath.

Nevertheless, Bankim's crusade against the epistemology of the empire is a fascinating topic of study, to which we now turn our attention.

Bankim Versus British

In irony and in earnest, Bankim was a nineteenth century personality. Rabindranath Tagore, on the other hand, for a little more than half of his life belonged to the twentieth century. The fact, that Babu Bankim Chandra Chattopadhyay acted as the midwife of Bengali nation-consciousness at a crucial juncture of our history, that he helped the Bengali babu garner an escape velocity from the giant gravitational pull of the British empire and set him free to imagine a nation in a state of independence, might be one of those commonplace hypotheses about which general agreement runs to such an extent, that it becomes mildly boring to re-examine the case and putting the hypothesis to fresh analytical test. We shall not do that, instead we shall have observe some important moments of clash between Bankim's project and the British empire.

In India, government services are still sometimes referred to as baboodom, thus remembering a not-so-remote past when the Bengali in his avatar as babu was ubiquitous as a motif of administration. The babu of the empire refers to the meaning of babu in Bengal, because throughout rest of India this word had multiple other meanings, the most common of them being a diminutive of father, which is evident in the Hindi word *babuji*, or in the use of babu as a middle name in different parts of north and south India. Only in Bengal, babu had this specific meaning: an official, a government executive, a position of authority, an elite class with western orientation.

The Bengali babu constituted an "intermediate ruling class" and as such came under fire from the neighbouring state of Orissa, as Suniti Kumar Chattopadhyay records an instance from twentieth century (198). Suniti Chatterjee missed an irony: such hateful reactions came to directed against Bengalis at a time when the Bengali elites in their collective political consciousness moved beyond baboodom, and were no longer a loyal British ally. Clearly, an imperial design against the Bengalis cannot be ruled out behind such xenophobic hatred, more so, from such peoples who continued to remain loyal to British.

Bankim's ghost continued to haunt the empire long after he was gone. A case in point is the British reaction against Bankim's song *Vande Mataram*. Sir Henry Craik, Head of the Home Department and member of the Viceroy's Executive Council made the following observation in 1937:

For many years the phrase 'Vande Mataram' has been literally the war cry of the terrorists in Bengal, and although the words simply mean 'Hail Mother' they are commonly shouted as a slogan by terrorists when committing outrages, and by others as an outward sign of sympathy with revolution and of defiance against Government. The song has really no claim to be regarded as a national song... (Sabyasachi Bhattacharya: 2003: 10)

Craik realized that it was not sufficient to negate the song on the grounds of sedition alone, and therefore significantly harped on the Muslim angle. He argued that Vande Mataram “actually originated as 'hymn of hate' against Muslims” (Sabyasachi Bhattacharya: 2003: 10).

The *Encyclopaedia Britannica* in its 1910 entry on Bankim Chandra notes that the novel *Anandamath* came in the wake of the Ilbert Bill agitations, and also observes that Vande Mataram was not used as a slogan during Bankim's lifetime, and only attained an “evil notoriety” after the emergence of anti-Partition movement (Sabyasachi Bhattacharya: 2003: 49-50). A Police report prepared by J E Armstrong in 1917 observes that “there is scarcely ever a revolutionary document that is not headed with Om Bandemataram” (Sabyasachi Bhattacharya: 2003: 49)

Sabyasachi Bhattacharya's study *Vande Mataram: The Biography of a Song* is a weak analysis of the fervour and the turbulence surrounding this song. He, for example completely missed the crucial role of Sarala Devi in mothering the political significance of Vande Mataram. Bhattacharya introduces Sarala in his study as “a Bengali lady” who was requested by G K Gokhale to sing Vande

Mataram at the Congress session at Benares in 1905: “The president of the Congress G K Gokhale requested a Bengali lady Saraladevi Chowdhurani to sing Vande Mataram. She was Rabindranath Tagore's niece and the wife of Rambhuj Dutta Chowdhury of Lahore, the editor of a nationalist Urdu weekly” (23). Curiously, Bhattacharya seems to have read Sarala's autobiography and he also quotes from there. Bhattacharya does not take any cognizance of the facts which Sarala records in her autobiography: that the members of the Suhrid Samiti, Mymensingh district, for the first time used Vande Mataram as a slogan and political cry for the first time in Bengal and in India, in a procession, when they came to receive Sarala from the rail station (53).

A relentless crusade against Orientalism is an important aspect of Bankim's writings. Kamalakanta in his opium induced dream observes the assault of the white men on the Sanskrit resources, and the assault is named Asiatic research by the white colonizers. As an employee of the colonial system, every battle that Bankim fought was an insider's battle. When he resisted British encroachment in discourses of history and culture, he was fighting from within: he was a part of colonial set up, first as a student of colonial education, and then as an employee of colonial administration. Further, when Bankim clashed with the babu in his satiric writings, he was putting up a challenge against his own tribe of western educated Bengalis. Moreover, when he was fighting against certain dubious strains of Hindu emergence, he was again fighting as an insider. Bankim belonged to a family of worshippers of Radhaballabh, a Vaishnava deity installed in the Chattopadhyay household for centuries. Fine details of the Radhaballabh temple, rituals and festivals of worship are given by Hemendrakumar Dasgupta in his biography of Bankim. Bankim's novel *Poison Tree* in its description of the *Thakurbari* (house of worship) of Nagendra Dutta was perhaps influenced by the memory of the Radhaballabh temple, as Jyotishchandra, Bankim's nephew (Bankim's elder brother Sanjibchandra's son) observed (Hemendranath Dasgupta 14-16)

An insider's struggle yields certain dividends while it also forces certain handicaps. Bankim was a product of colonial education; he was shaped by the contemporary West even as he waged a

relentless war against the same forces which had formative influence on him. Hemendranath Dasgupta observes that by the age of eleven, Bankim finished reading all the major histories of Europe available those days (“রররোললিয়রোস সরোহহেহবের সমস পরোচচীন ইলতিহেরোস, লহেউহমর ইইংলিলরোহভের ইলতিহেরোস পভভলতি পপুসকঅলতি যত সহেরোরোহর আদলন পরোঠ কলরয়রোলছিহলিন”). Hemendranth notes in the same vein that Bankim exhibited “excellence in English and History” (68).

He was surrounded by the epistemology of the empire from an early age, yet he developed an ironical reflection on those surroundings. One of the earliest critical responses to the empire coming from the childhood of Bankim as recorded by his biographer Shachishchandra Chattopadhyay takes us back to a six-year-old Bankim. Bankim's father was promoted to be a Deputy Collector in Medinipur district in 1844, and Bankim was admitted to the District English school. One day, a street performer was passing by the school with his pet monkey. Bankim went to see the monkey and then he reported to have remarked, “If only that monkey could be admitted to our class, I'd like to see if it could pick up some English” (24).

Bankim's attempts to revisit his indigenous legacy and recover his roots (no doubt influenced by trends on contemporary Europe) elicit our gratitude. No analysis of the possible indebtedness of Bankim's *Vande Mataram* to his predecessors from the perspective of cultural history has been produced till date, and we shall not try to attempt that here, as it is beyond our present scope. But it should be a crucial area of study because through such influences, the bygone era continued to communicate with the future, Bankim's pen acting as the medium. While the song might have been indebted to the lyric of a then popular hymn to the Goddess of the River Ganges that children used to recite from a primer named *Shishubodhok*, as a memoir of Amritalal Basu notes. The hymn went like this: *Bondo Mata Surodhoni, Purane Mohima Shuni, Potitopaboni Puratoni* (বেন মরোতিরো সপুর্খনচী, পপুর্রোহণ

মলাহেমরো শুলন, পলতিতিপরোবেনচী পপুর্রোতিনচী), roughly translated as all hail mother, the divine river, we hear about your greatness in the *puranas*, you are ancient and salvation of sinners). Basu used to chant this hymn

which formed a part of his childhood lesson, and of numerous other children of that generation prior to the emergence of the monopoly of the primer text authored by Vidyasagar, *Bornoporichoy*. Basu believed that *Bondo Mata* (literally meaning “all hail the mother”) was the ancestry (*adipurush*) of Bankim's Vande Mataram (39).

I shall suggest that a specific line of Vande Mataram song, *Obola Keno Ma Eto Bole* (why powerless, mother, with so much power), the revised version of which runs as *Ke Bole Ma Tumi Obole* (who says mother you are powerless) exhibits an obvious influence of Ishwar Gupta, whose poetry was precisely known for such alliteration and repetition of sounds. The Sanskrit lyric evokes an ambiance of the ancient, apart from bestowing the song with a unifying contemporary impetus. As such, through Bankim's Vande Mataram, the past generations successfully interacted, connived and conspired with the future generations against a common enemy: colonization. It is not the focus of our present study, again, but the indebtedness of the Vande Mataram song to Bankim's early poetic training under Ishwar Gupta's tutelage can be an exciting area of close analysis, something which has not been attempted yet.

Bankim fought the empire on many fronts, and epistemology was the most crucial of them. The might of the empire was manifested in its modern experimental science. and Bankim realized that it was important to appraise the Bengalis about modern developments in science. He undertook a lengthy project to write about popular science.

Very few nationalities of the world in their history can boast of a revivalist icon who also aggressively pushed for scientific awareness among masses, familiarizing them with latest developments in science and technology. I cannot think of a comparable figure from Irish revival, for example.

Bankim was aware of the limited benefits of the empire as well. He did not deny that the British advent has been an instrument of progress in Indian history (as he observed, British taught new things and brought down old structures of prejudice, inequality and superstition prevalent among

Hindus). However, there was a steep price that India had to pay for that progress-by-colonization. The bloodshed, the humiliation and the exploitation constituted a huge landscape which became the canvass for an emerging nation-consciousness challenging foreign domination. But unlike, for example, a Gandhian aversion to modern science, Bankim embraced science whole-heartedly.

Bankim's increasing bitter experience in service following the publication of *Anandamath* is chronicled in details by Shishir Kar's study. Bankim was demoted in service, he was harangued. Throughout his life within the colonial apparatus, there were plenty of incidents when he was insulted – even physically abused – and under consistent attacks by the white colonizers. When his literary endeavours were deemed dangerous by the authorities, he was given extra burden of work, precisely because his writings as well as publication of *Bongodorshon* were sought to be stopped by the imperial administration (Kar 67).

Quite humiliatingly, Bankim had to go asking for a certificate from Keshub Chunder Sen's brother Krishnobihari to the effect that the text of *Anandamath* did not inspire treason against British, else its publication and Bankim's career – both were facing imminent doom (Kar 69). Bankim's premature retirement at the age of fifty-three owes to this continuous pressure in his working life which left him drained out. This life full of stress could have been the reason behind his diabetes and early death.

Age of bhadralok would be a movement of the Bengalis away from civil services, a development epitomized by Subhash Bose's abandonment of ICS. No comprehensive data analysis in this regard exists, but during this period Bengalis continually valued independent intellectuals: be it writers, professors, doctors, engineers, artists. Bankim's career was probably a lasting lesson for the impending age of bhadralok. Civil services would not be a preferred vocation for the bhadralok who would value his independence, because he carried Bankim's memory within his political unconscious; that memory knew what it was like to be in chains.

Bankim's Clash with Vidyasagar

We have two known occasions when Vidyasagar was examiner (i.e. paper-setter and checker of answer scripts) and Bankim as a student performed poorly in the Bengali paper: in the first graduation examination after the establishment of Calcutta University in 1857; and even before that, in the Hooghly College Senior Division Examination of 1852. Records tell us (as reported by Bankim's biographer Amitrasudan) that on both the occasions, Vidyasagar was the examiner of the Bengali paper, and that he did not like Bankim's Bengali to the point where he chose to fail him. Bankim was known to excel in all his examinations otherwise (in Hooghly College he passed all the examinations with scholarly distinction, barring 1852, as Bankim's biographer Hemendra Dasgupta attests: the examination of 1852 he passed nonetheless, but without scholarship, owing to the debacle in the Bengali paper).

The only known instances of Bankim's "failure" as a student come from these two papers of Bengali. Barring Bankim's poor performance in the combined language paper of Calcutta university (which had English and Bengali; W Grapel was the examiner of the English paper where Bankim performed very well, but he had to pass with grace marks in the Bengali portion that was checked by Vidyasagar), he performed brilliantly in all other papers (including History, Mathematics, Natural History, Natural Philosophy and Physical Science).

Bankim was already a published poet by 1853 in Ishwar Gupta's *Shongbad Probhakor*, so his Bengali could not have been that weak so as to deserve a failure. Bankim's Bengali was perhaps different from the conservative style of Vidyasagar. We have already seen that Bankim was opposed to Bidyashagori Bangla.

Bankim has been blamed for opposing Vidyasagar's social reforms, though that might not constitute a valid allegation. A character of *Bishbrikkho* (Poison Tree), Surjomukhi, speaks out against Vidyasagar and widow remarriage, but that cannot be construed as a political statement of the writer himself. Bankim in fact registered his support for widow remarriage in unequivocal terms

in his article *Samyo*. Then, there is a widespread misconception that Vidyasagar's movement against polygamy was opposed by Bankim. Bankim, on the contrary, supported it in his concerned article on polygamy, albeit with some riders. He criticized Vidyasagar's movement to be Quixotic which was charging at a windmill: polygamy was dying out as a practice in any case, and Vidyasagar's account of it was inflated, Bankim maintains. Then Bankim added something which was far more significant than the first rider: scriptural justification is not required for social reform. If a reform needs to be done for the benefit of society, it should proceed without looking for scriptural justification.

This was a revolutionary proposition in all its dimensions, and I want to argue that it was a signal contribution of Bankim towards the freedom of thought in the intellectual orientation of the age of bhadrakalok. That the bhadrakalok was remarkably freed from Hindu religious dogma was attributable to that courageous pronouncement of the man who himself was the greatest intellectual icon of the Hindu revival of nineteenth century. Prior to Bankim, major intellectuals like Rammohan and Vidyasagar always submitted to the authority of the book.

The challenge to the authority of Vedas in Bengal posed by Samkhya and Tantra must have been a close topic of study for Bankim. Under such circumstances, the polyphonic nature of Hinduism does not allow a rigid scriptural regime. Further, customs and conventions always have taken precedence over scriptural texts in Hinduism. Moreover, as a cumulative result of Bengal Renaissance, the nascent class of middle class intellectuals increasingly supported atheism. Bankim was a part of the momentum of the new middle classes who will no longer be unquestioningly shackled to the authority of scriptures.

Bankim continued to maintain this position. Towards the end of his life, when he was asked about the propriety of sea voyage for Hindus, Bankim, in his letter to Binoykrishno Deb, said:

I am not a theologian, and I am not ready to take the place of one. But I have no objection to speak a word or two about the agitation that has come up regarding sea voyage.

Firstly, I do not believe that any social reform can be or should be done by evoking the authority of religious scriptures. When the late *Mahatma* Vidyasagar started a movement against polygamy by evoking the authority of scriptures, I raised the same objection, and I have no reason to change that opinion till now. There are two reasons behind my consideration. First, *Bengali* society is loyal to folk customs or customs of the land, and not loyal to scriptures. It's true that folk customs sometimes follow scriptures. But more often they do not follow scriptures, and when there is a conflict between custom and scripture, custom prevails.

The second reason behind my aforesaid conviction is that it is doubtful whether society will benefit, if it always follows the ruling of the scriptures. (*Bankim Rochonaboli* 2: 858)

We need to remember here that Bankim wanted uniform civil code in his article on polygamy. He said that if there is a social reform, then it should be applicable for every inhabitant of Bengal, and not just Hindus alone, and that constituted a part of Bankim's objection to evoking Hindu scriptural authority in social reforms.

The clash between Bankim and Vidyasagar, when closely studied, reveals that there can be only one possible objection against Bankim: but that would be a little subtextual, and will require reading between the lines. It could be the case that Bankim was opposed to these imperially aided social reforms. Law-making was a domain entirely and exclusively controlled by the British imperial government, and Bankim might have tried to resist Vidyasagar's attempt to bring the colonial administration to yet another intervention into Hindu social life. If that subtext was there, then Bankim was being a crafty advocate. But that possibility of a subtext is cancelled by Bankim's

consistent, continuing stand of opposing scriptural authority vis-à-vis reforms, as displayed by his stand regarding sea-voyage, which establishes it beyond doubt that his position was sincere: that he objected to Vidyasagar from a position of sincerity and not obfuscation.

It is interesting that the process of colonial history was dissolving the authority of Hinduism as a whole. Not just scriptures alone, but folk customs too were losing grounds. There is one much maligned line from Ishwar Gupta which is very often quoted as a proof of Gupta's misogyny and opposition to female education (he was *not* opposed to female education, and was in fact an enthusiastic supporter of the same, as multiple contemporary accounts show: I discussed that in details in my article on Ishwar Gupta in JBS Kolkata issue), the translation of which reads like this: "As the young girls pick up books in their hands and learn A and B, they will soon turn into replicas of European women and will roam freely in the open field adjacent to the British fort in Kolkata" (my apologies for this thoroughly unpoetic translation).

What is usually given a miss is that Gupta's poem records a lamentation: that the English education will deprive the girls from their roots, from the *broto*s which formed an integral part of Bengali feminine customs (feminine ritual chants to commemorate certain celestial, mostly solar and some lunar events of the calendar, worship of deities etc). Gupta asks: will the educated girls ever again sing the *broto* of *Shanjh-Shejuti*?

The intellectual colonization inherent in Macaulay's education system – and we need to remember that Vidyasagar himself was an integral part of that system – was already showing its results. Bankim writes in his "Confessions of a Young Bengal":

Our Deism, our Theism, our Brahmoism, progressive or ultra-progressive, our Comp[sic]teism – apparently an indigenous religious development, the morality of which was recently discussed, under that strange designation, with equal ability and learning in

more than one issue of a Calcutta newspaper – what are all these *isms* at bottom but merely so many different embodiments of a strong desire to exempt ourselves from the obligations of Hinduism. (*Essays and Letters* 93)

This is a Janus-faced paradox, a strange hypocrisy that lies at the heart of the genesis of the age of bhadralok: the social reforms of Vidyasagar evoked the authority of scriptures whereas Bankim, the Hindu revivalist advocated for a freedom from scriptures.

In this regard, an interesting observation was made by Rakhal Chandra Nath in his article “Bankim Ki Protikriyashil Chilen?” compiled in *Poshchimbongo* Bankim issue of 1995. He records a lengthy list of hypocrisies of the liberal-*bishshomanob* icons of Bengal Renaissance, like Rammohan and Vidyasagar. Nath proceeds in a rather iconoclastic manner, and then contrasts Bankim with them. I shall not go into the details, as that would be outside our focus in this article, but Nath makes some valid observations, and truly, if Bankim was remarkably free from one single vice, then it was a complete abstinence from hypocrisy. He knew how to reconcile pragmatism with ethics, compulsions of history with the necessities of community. A continuous ironical impulse ensured that he even maintained a critical distance from the ideologies which were prevalent, including those of his own class, and like a giant whose strength was immense, Bankim did not need to resort to hypocrisy and could always afford to be straightforward in his non-fictional writings.

Bankim’s Clash with Hinduism?

An anxious question that Bankim’s “Confessions of a Young Bengal” asks in its conclusion, is this:

[S]ound logic compels us to cry with one voice, Hinduism must be destroyed. Agreed. But

the spiritual nature of man abhors a vacuum. Between our various *isms*, the Hindu code of personal and social ethics has been well-nigh wholly repealed, and its precepts are universally seen and felt to be more honoured in the breach than in the observance. Where is our new code of morality? Where is the new public opinion to enforce its rules? (*Essays and Letters* 93)

Bankim himself did exhibit an indifferent, and mildly hostile attitude to Hinduism in his early career at least on one occasion. *Rajmohan's Wife* while describing the interiors of the bedchamber of Mathur Ghose, casually observes: "Two paintings of the largest size, from one of which glowered the grim black figure of Kali, and on the other of which was displayed the crab-like form of Durga, faced each other from high positions on two opposite walls" (77).

The obvious threat coming from an Anglocentric worldview was that it would make the educated Bengalis see their own culture from the white colonizer's viewpoint. Bankim inhabited the belly of the beast during this period, but he would eventually come out of that.

The legendary interview between Bankim and Ramakrishna Paramahansa which took place in 1884 (as recorded in the Gospels of Ramakrishna) did not go well. The description does not do justice to Bankim's viewpoints. A reader of the *Kathamrita* might end up forming quite negative opinions about Bankim. However, it cannot be disputed that *Kathamrita* is very often one-sided. It is written to give the perspective of the Ramakrishna movement. While we do not have Bankim's account of that encounter, a few points should be considered.

When Bankim meets Ramakrishna, the saint makes a joke out of Bankim's name: "What weight has caused you to bend?" (Bankim literally means bent or curved, and hence the joke). Bankim responded that the weight of the shoes of the British.

Bankim's quest for the answers to the fundamental riddles of life did not lead him to spirituality.

Bankim in his memoir recorded his anxious search for the meaning of life in his early youth when he used to ask: *E Jibon Loiya Ki Koribo, E Jibon Loiya Ki Korite Hoy?* (What shall I do with this life? What is one supposed to do with this life?). When Bankim responded to Ramkrishna's question about the purpose and meaning of life with the answer *aahaar, nidra, moithun* that is, food, sleep and sex – it caused consternation, embarrassment and scandal. *Kathamrita* tells us that Ramkrishna asked for meaning of human life and not just any life, but to my eyes it looks a little doubtful. A rhetorical question about the purpose of life, in anticipation of a lofty answer (Ramkrishna in all likelihood wanted to hear that the purpose of life is a quest for God, or Divinity, which would be evident to any sincere reader of *Kothamrito*) would surely draw some satire from Bankim, the keen observer of human nature. Bankim's answer would have a bare factual correctness, even if the question was about human life. Human life as a form of animal life abides by the basic universal principles of living organisms.

Further, Bankim was answering to the question about purpose of life in a solidly materialistic, blasé and nonchalant way. Humans are different from the rest of the animal kingdom in certain complex ways, and Bankim was aware of that. However, Bankim's intellect resisted all forms of idealism, while the Ramakrishna movement was founded on idealism. It is also significant that Bankim never sought the meaning of life in a spiritual solace, abandoning reason, history and community.

To that extent, the political ideology of Vivekananda is more indebted to Bankim than to his mentor Ramakrishna himself. Vivekananda's brother Bhupendranath Dutt acknowledged that in his account of Vivekananda's political thought. It can be argued that Vivekananda's conception of Ramakrishna Mission as an organization is indebted to Bankim's *Anandamath*. Ramkrishna in any case was concerned with the individual's spiritual salvation in the fashion of classical Samkhya philosophy. *Kathamrita* makes it obvious at a number of places that Ramakrishna viewed a dissociation of purush and prakriti as a prerequisite for salvation.

Ramakrishna's idea of collective education for the folks was supposed to bring spiritual salvation, and not national or collective empowerment. Ramakrishna was not concerned about any collective entity called nation, folk, people, community. Ramakrishna was not known to be critical of the empire and colonization. Vivekananda the nationalist is a creation of Bankim's legacy, it can be argued. Hemchandra Ghosh, the founder of Bengal Volunteers reminisces of his meeting with Vivekananda in 1901 when the latter told him: "Read Bankim Chandra – Bankim Chandra – and Bankim Chandra only" (Dey 1: 2)

But let us go back to that celebrated conflict of ideas. We need to realize that Ramakrishna did not just meet Bankim, but over a period, he held interviews with a number of Kolkata dignitaries. The interview with Keshub Chunder Sen was highly successful and it led to a number of future meetings between these two. But Ramakrishna's interviews with Vidyasagar and Bankim ended disastrously, and they never met again. Ramakrishna had a spiritual agenda and these two were men of intellect. This can be seen as a conventional clash between Jnanamarga and Bhaktimarga, the path of knowledge and the path of devotion. Bankim's choice for the path of knowledge over the path of devotion influenced the future course of the age of bhadralok.

Language of reason has a universal applicability, transcending the barriers of limited and esoteric languages of idealism which are limited to specific groups. The spirituality of Ramakrishna movement is a unique language of that movement, and might not be acceptable to those who are outside it. It has been suggested that human beings invented the faculty of reason in order to speak with strangers. It would be an interesting hypothetical spectacle of anthropology to behold early humans developing reasoning and arguing faculties as a method of communicating with others who did not belong to the same bloodline, same tribe and same culture.²

Bankim's project is marked by an emphasis on reason and a denial of idealism. This might have paved the way for the age of bhadralok to have its international reach. Bengalis have frequently been the international face of India throughout modern history. They have communicated with the

rest of the world with an effortless ease, and the reason why Bengalis were able to do so, might, at least partially, lie in Bankim. In choosing reason and knowledge over spiritual salvation, Bankim made a choice, and it influenced the following generations. Through his seasoned reasoning, as the literary monarch of his era, Bankim shaped the consciousness of educated Bengalis like nobody else. The age of bhadralok was the age of reason. And it was this legacy of reasoning which made the bhadralok an internationalist in outlook and exposure, just the way a language influences our ways of seeing the world.

Bankim's brief encounter with Shoshodhor Torkochuramoni (a vocal proponent of Hindu revivalism, who absurdly observed that all Hindu rituals, myths and customs had their support in modern science) is an excellent example of his clash with Hindu dogmatism. While Bankim himself was an enthusiastic proponent of reconciliation between science and Hinduism (his article "On the Origin of Hindu Festivals" compiled in *Essays and Letters* deals with the impeccable astronomy of the Hindu festivals of antiquity), he soon became wary of Torkochuramoni's fanciful ideas of scientific Hinduism. An anecdote from contemporary sources narrates how Agastya's evaporation of the sea was described by Shoshodhor Torkochuramoni as the breaking down of water into hydrogen and oxygen by the electric current emanating from the sage's eyes. The fact that the bhadralok abandoned any belief in such absurd things which the rest of India still sometimes subscribes to this day (Ganesh's elephant head claimed to be an example of plastic surgery is a contemporary re-incarnation of Shoshodhor's methodology) is attributable to Bankim as the architect of the age of bhadralok. Bankim was initially enthusiastic about Shoshodhor and he also took the troubles to introduce Shoshodhor to the people of Kolkata. Shoshodhor was a good orator, and Ramakrishna is said to have remarked after meeting Shoshodhor that he has been able to see the second moon (that is a meaning of the name Shoshodhor). Shoshodhor insisted that Hindus must carry the external insignia of devotion: the sacred mark on forehead (*tilok*) and the tuft of hair on rear-head (*tiki*) must be worn. Shoshodhor gave fantastical explanations in favour of such Hindu practices, which were

now touted to be scientific. Bankim disagreed and dissociated from Shoshodhor. Bankim was never a dogmatic Hindu, and the age of bhadrakal would carry that legacy. As if his absurd claims about science were not enough, Shoshodhor in his revivalist zeal wanted to reduce Hinduism to a set of restrictions and commandments about food, dress, get up and everyday life. Bankim looked forward to a Hinduism which was worthier than that.³

Coda

Bankim was not a figure like imperial Russia's celebrated historian Nikolai Karamzin, whose twelve-volume history of Russia remains a beloved work to this day, and yet Bankim is considered to have fathered modern Bengali historiography. In spite of his authorship of *Vande Mataram*, Bankim was not a legendary poet like Goethe or Shakespeare or Tagore, for whom the status of a seer is usually reserved. Still, Bankim is known among common Bengalis with the appellation *rishi*, or seer, who witnessed the revelation of the śloka *Vande Mataram* (the hymns of Rigveda manifested and revealed themselves to the rishis who then uttered them as chants, as per the Vedic legends). Bankim had a short life, and his job as deputy magistrate did not allow him to devote his time completely to literature, and yet he remains an infinite source of our cultural history. Rabindranath's greatness is writ large on the wall of fame: he was Brahmo, he came from the Tagore clan, he was awarded Nobel prize in literature, he founded the establishment of VisvaBharati, he was one of the most prolific writers of world literature; Bankim's greatness is not so much favoured by his circumstances (which were often adverse to him), but by his sheer commitment to his people against insurmountable odds.

Bankim and Rabindranath ruled Bengali culture in succession; they were the two iconic figures who dominated Bengal Renaissance. However question-begging the term Bengal Renaissance might have become as a category, as a period of our modern history stretching from Rammohan to

Rabindranath, as a period of fermentation and mutation, it primarily remains a site of dialectics. At the end of the day, it was an intense period of clash of ideas. When we try to understand the long twentieth century of Bengal, the early part of which overlaps with Bengal Renaissance, we need to remember that it was primarily shaped by the legacies of these conflicts. The conflicts involving Bankim and Rabindranath left behind very important legacies which the age of bhadrakalok was made of, as this article has tried to show.

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2. See Paul Rabinow's *Essays on the Anthropology of Reason* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1996).
3. <http://www.anandabazar.com/editorial/%E0%A6%B8%E0%A6%AE-%E0%A6%AA-%E0%A6%A6%E0%A6%95-%E0%A6%B8%E0%A6%AE-%E0%A6%AA-%E0%A6%B7-1.60218>

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